

A STUDY ON THE FILTRATION PROPERTIES AND PEEL-OFF DURABILITY OF BAG FILTER MEDIA LAMINATED WITH PTFE MEMBRANES

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1. Introduction

Entering the era of rapidly growing industries, the harmful dust particles, dioxin and heavy metals are causing environmental pollution throughout discharging combustion process, automobile emission, incineration process and industrial sectors.

The fine dust particles are mainly occurred as the production of industrial products, the combustion process and the destruction of solid materials. The filtration/electrical collector equipments are utilized to remove the fine dust particles such as soot and a dust. They are used for the recovery of raw materials that are discharged in the process and cleaning air which affects product's quality [1-2]. The fine dust size is between 0.1 μm and 20 μm . The air streams contaminated with particulate matter must be cleaned before discharge to the atmosphere, because the particulate matter may have adverse effects on human and animal health, as well as plants [3-4]. The filter bag used in filtration/electrical collector equipments has been made of the natural fibers like cotton or wool in the past, but recently these materials are getting replaced into synthetic fibers/nonwovens [5-7]. The properties of PTFE membranes include excellent charge storage stability, good mechanical property, very low average mass density and high water vapor transmission. Regardless of the sort of dust or working conditions, bag filter shows extremely high power. For the reason of this, electric dust collect system is replaced by bag filter. however, under the high temperature over 250 degree and serious wear and tear conditions, It could happen the problems like deformation and surface damaged by the high temperature on existing dust filter media [2-6].

In this study, we characterized the filtration properties and peel-off durability of the bag filter

media that were prepared by laminating the glass fabric with PTFE membranes.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

Commercially available glass fabric(A) was used as substrate of composite filter bag media. The high temperature PTFE composite membrane filters are prepared by combining PTFE membrane and substrate using the laminating equipment. Three types of membranes were used. They were dense, bulky and high bulky types. The composite filters were manufactured under low and high pressure condition of the laminating process. Also, glass fabric(B)-nonwoven(C) was used as substrate for peel-off durability evaluation. They were manufactured changed pressure of the laminating process with same membrane type

2.2 Performance evaluation

The filtration properties evaluation of the filter bag by membrane structure was carried out with the membrane structure, air permeability and filtration efficiency using TSI (Fractional Efficiency Filter tester), PMI (Capillary Flow Porometer), SEM (Scanning Electron Microscope), Bag Filter Media Performance Evaluation Equipment. The peel-off durability evaluation of the filter bag media surface change was carried with Peel-off Durability Evaluation Equipment.

3. Results and discussion

Figure 1. SEM images of PTFE membrane filter bag media; (a)low pressure and dense type, (b)low pressure and bulky type, (c)low pressure and high bulky type, (d)high pressure and dense type

Figure 1 shows the morphologies of the prepared composite filter by laminating PTFE membranes. From Figure 1, (a) was similar to (d) in morphology, and (b) was to (c). The results of the TSI and the PMI on the PTFE membrane composite filter were summarized in Table 1 and Table 2. The composite filter media samples manufactured with dense type membrane under high pressure of lamination showed excellent efficiency and small pore size, while differential pressure was relatively higher than other samples. This is due to the high pressure at laminating. Compare with fabric type and nonwoven type, membrane type shows similar efficiency but higher differential pressure than nonwoven. Also, Poer size of the data in Table 1 are similar to differential pressure. B-type media is shown small pore size. The mean flow pore diameter of Sample (A-1) shows 1.02. It is greater than Sample (A-4) that is 0.61, because (A-4) is manufactured by laminating with high pressure. The data in Table 3 shows the filtration efficiencies of the PTFE membrane composite filter bag media. From Table 3, sample (A-1) showed the best performance since it could run 100 of the filtration cycles without reaching specified threshold pressure while other samples could not. (A-1), (B-5), (C-1), (C-2) medias show excellent property on filtration cycles of 100 times in filter bag filtration properties.

Especially, B-5 media shows the smallest dust mass total filter and Mean dust concentration in clean gas values. Because of this property, it is considered the best filter bag media. Figure 2 shows peel-off durability by laminating PTFE membranes with glass fabric(B). Peel-off phenomenon was not observe in the case of non-woven fabric. Nonwoven was a lot of coated membrane than glass fabric. Therefore, nonwoven did not observe peel-off phenomenon by the pressure of the air spraying. Because the adhesion area of nonwoven between PTFT membrane and the substrate is larger than glass fabric, it is considered not to peel off under the same air spraying pressure.

4. Conclusions

This study presents experimental results and it was able to find the appropriate process conditions based on filtration and peel-off durability properties. The composites filter made with dense type membrane under low pressure laminating condition showed the best.

Sample	Efficiency (% , 0.3 μm)	Resistance (mmH2O)
A-1	87.4	23.9
A-2	99.7	20.8
A-3	94.6	15.5
A-4	99.6	48.7
B-1	99.4	56.8
B-2	98.0	49.3
B-3	98.0	45.1
B-4	98.9	44.4
B-5	98.9	35.0
C-1	98.7	19.4
C-2	98.5	20.9
C-3	99.0	26.8
C-4	97.7	34.5
C-5	98.6	20.8
C-6	98.2	34.0
C-7	98.0	31.5

Table 1. TSI results of PTFE membrane filter bag media

Sample	Mean Flow Pore Pressure (PSI)	Mean Flow Pore Diameter (μm)	Bubble Point Pressure (PSI)	Bubble Point Pore Diameter (μm)
A-1	6.479	1.02	0.073	91.59
A-2	7.303	0.91	0.443	15.01
A-3	2.852	2.33	0.415	16.00
A-4	10.931	0.61	0.505	13.15
B-1	10.82	0.61	0.12	55.3
B-2	10.57	0.63	0.79	8.41
B-3	9.80	0.68	0.32	20.59
B-4	10.99	0.60	0.27	25.06
B-5	10.70	0.62	0.44	15.26
C-1	6.30	1.05	0.24	27.96
C-2	4.05	4.64	0.11	63.24
C-3	6.16	1.08	0.87	7.65
C-4	4.87	1.36	0.22	30.53
C-5	4.95	1.34	0.36	18.32
C-6	5.08	1.31	0.18	37.94
C-7	6.52	1.02	0.32	20.75

Table 2. PMI results of PTFE membrane filter bag media

Sample	Filtration cycles	Total duration (h:mm:ss)	Dust mass on total filter(mg)	Mean dust concentration in clean gas(mg/m^3)
A-1	100	1:55:39	0.6	0.098
A-2	92	1:35:03	0.2	0.040
A-3	30	0:34:00	0.1	0.055
A-4	38	0:46:51	0.2	0.080
B-1	28	0:18:15	0.1	0.103
B-2	27	0:22:03	0.3	0.256
B-3	57	0:54:57	0.1	0.034
B-4	51	0:48:27	0.1	0.039
B-5	100	1:22:54	0.2	0.045
C-1	100	1:40:27	1.7	0.318

C-2	100	1:48:27	0.7	0.121
C-3	28	0:28:42	0.4	0.262
C-4	11	0:12:54	0.1	0.146
C-5	76	0:55:54	0.1	0.034
C-6	4	0:05:48	-	-
C-7	25	0:19:27	0.2	0.193

Table 3. Filtration efficiencies of PTFE membrane filter bag media

Figure 2. Images of PTFE membrane filter bag media

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